

References

1. The Wealth of India, Raw Materials, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, Vol. IV, 1956, 108.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, 123.
3. L. RAMCHANDRA RAO, M. GOPALA RAO and C. RUKMINI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 1203.
4. T. R. SHESHADRI and K. J. BALAKRISHNA, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 91, 260.
5. K. VENKATARAMAN and A. V. RAMARAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 677.
6. K. VENKATARAMAN, A. V. RAMARAO, P. CHAKRABARTI, A. K. SANYAL and P. K. BOSE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 398.

Iodine Promoted Thermal Cyclisation of Anthranilic Acid

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DIPHENYLAMINE(I) and aniline(II) were shown to cyclise to carbazole(III) under iodine promoted thermal cyclisation^{1,2}. Aniline was, however shown to give host of other products including diphenylamine. Recently Bradenberger *et al*³ have shown that aniline cyclises to diphenylamine and carbazole. In consideration of our interest in the Rutaceae alkaloids^{4,5} of anthranilate origin⁶, we were interested to investigate the fate of anthranilic acid(IV) under this oxidative cyclisation reaction. In the present communication, we report the formation of diphenylamine(I), carbazole(III), acridone(V) and *o*-aminobenzophenone(VI) as significant products by iodine promoted thermal cyclisation of (IV).

Anthranilic acid was heated in a sealed tube containing oxygen and trace of iodine at 350° for 3 hours. The reaction products were taken up in benzene, fractionated into basic and neutral fractions and then chromatographed over alumina. From the neutral fractions diphenylamine(I) mp 56° ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 240, 286 nm with log ϵ 3.90, 4.22), carbazole(III) mp 230° ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 233, 257, 293 nm with log ϵ 4.5, 4.18, 4.10) were isolated. These form the major products of reactions. From the basic fraction acridone, mp 354° ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 251, 254, 295, 308, 370, 381, 400 nm with log ϵ 4.76, 4.78, 3.33, 3.05, 3.63, 3.93, 3.95) and *o*-aminobenzophenone mp 103° ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 234 nm with log ϵ 4.37) were isolated.

All these compounds were identified by comparison with authentic specimens by t.l.c., mmp., and uv spectra. The formation of (I) and (III) from (II) is well documented^{2,3}. They could arise here from (IV) by ready decarboxylation of (IV) to (II) and subsequent cyclisation. The formation of *o*-aminobenzophenone could be conceived to arise by the acylation of benzene fragment. The formation of aminobenzophenone by deamination of aniline through a benzyne intermediate⁷ cannot be ruled out.

The formation of the skeletal units (V, VI) of some of the alkaloids of Rutaceae by oxidative cyclisation of anthranilic acid and related compounds, the biogenetic hypothesis of the formation of acridone alkaloid from VI by Bowen *et al*⁸ and the recent report of Tecleanone (IX) in *Teclea grandifolia* open out the question of the formation of these alkaloids alternatively by oxidative cyclisation of anthranilic acid or its derivative under the biochemical interactions of appropriate oxidative enzymes.

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References

1. A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Chem. comm.* 1972, 537.
2. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. ISLAM and (Miss) M. SARKAR, *Proc. 5th International Symp. on the Chemistry of Natural Products*, held at Ljubljana, Yugoslavia, 1975, 341.

NOTES

3. C. T. ADAMS, S. G. BRADENBERGER, J. B. DUBOIS, G. S. MILL, M. NAGER and D. B. RICHARDSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 1.
4. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1977, **34**, 299.
5. R. S. KAPIL, "The Alkaloids" edited by R. H. F. MANSKE, 1971, **13**, 301.
6. J. R. PRICE, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1956, **13**, 302.
7. M. STILES, R. G. MILLER and U. BURCKHARDT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1792.
8. I. H. BOWEN, P. GUPTA and J. R. LEWIS, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 1625.
9. A. C. CASEY and A. MALHOTRA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1975, 401.